

A DSO flexibility platform based on an optimal congestion management model for the European CoordiNet project

Fernando García-Muñoz^a, Anzhelika Ivanova^a, Jordi Farre^a, Manel Serrano^a and Cristina Corchero^a

^aIREC Catalonia Institute for Energy Research, C. Jardins de les Dones de Negre, 1, Pl. 2a, 08930 Sant Adrià del Besòs, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Increasing penetration of distributed energy resources (DER) is pushing to increase the coordination between the transmission system operator (TSO) and the distribution system operator (DSO) to improve the power systems efficiency for active distribution network (DN) scenarios. In this context, the European CoordiNet project seeks to develop tools to measure the potential benefit of efficient TSO-DSO coordination in Greece, Spain, and Sweden networks, considering demand response, storage systems, and small-scale generation. This article presents the TSO-DSO coordination framework for the Spanish demonstration through developing a DSO platform that manages the services provided by the DERs, maintaining the congestion and voltage level in the operational ranges for the day-ahead and intraday markets. Thus, a deterministic mixed-integer non-linear model, based on the AC-OPF, is introduced for congestion management in two Spanish DNs (MV and MV/LV). The operational model constraints and the MV and MV/LV networks have been validated using the power system modeling software PandaPower. The results show that the DSO platform developed under the CoordiNet project guidelines allows for managing congestion and voltage issues at the distribution level through the flexibility provided by the DERs.

1. Introduction

The increasing penetration of small and medium-scale distributed generation and battery storage systems in the distribution system are pushing to evolve the current distribution system operator (DSO) role to more active coordination with the transmission system operator (TSO) to manage congestion, voltage, and frequency network problems. In this regard, the following section presents different market mechanisms and collaborative schemes studied over the last few years to

 fgarcia@irec.cat (F. García-Muñoz)
ORCID(s): 0000-0001-9376-4357 (F. García-Muñoz)

Nomenclature

Sets

- $i \in \mathcal{B}$ Set of buses
 $t \in \mathcal{T}$ Set of time slots.
 $k \in \Omega$ Set of type of generation source.
 $(i, j) \in \mathcal{L}$ Set of lines, such that $\mathcal{L} = \{(i, j); i, j \in \mathcal{B}\}$.

Parameters

- $\overline{PG}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Maximum active power output of the FSP k in bus i [%].
 $\overline{PL}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Maximum active power load of the FSP k in bus i [kW].
 $\underline{PL}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Minimum active power load of the FSP k in bus i [kW].
 PL_i^g Fixed active grid load of bus i [kW].
 PG_i^{sg} Active power output of the static generator in bus i [kW].
 $PG_{i,k}^a$ Active power auction of the FSP k in bus i [kW].
 $PL_{i,k}^a$ Active power load auction of the FSP k in bus i [kW].
 $\overline{QG}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Maximum reactive power output of the FSP k in bus i [%].
 $\underline{QG}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Minimum reactive power output of the FSP k in bus i [%].
 \overline{QG}_i^{ssh} Maximum reactive power output of the switched shunt in bus i [kVAr].
 \underline{QG}_i^{ssh} Minimum reactive power output of the switched shunt in bus i [kVAr].
 $\overline{QL}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Maximum reactive power load of the FSP k in bus i [kVAr].
 $\underline{QL}_{i,k}^{fs}$ Minimum reactive power load of the FSP k in bus i [kVAr].
 QL_i^g Fixed reactive grid load of bus i [kVAr].
 QG_i^{sg} Reactive power output of a static generator in bus i [kVAr].
 $QG_{i,k}^a$ Reactive power auction of the FSP k in bus i [kVAr].
 $QL_{i,k}^a$ Reactive power load auction of the FSP k in bus i [kW].

- V_i^{min} Allowed minimum voltage magnitude of bus i [p.u].
 V_i^{max} Allowed maximum voltage magnitude of bus i [p.u].
 V^0 Reference voltage [p.u].
 $S_{i,j}^{max}$ Allowed maximum apparent power of the line between buses i and j [kVA].
 $SL_{i,j}$ Maximum line safety capacity between buses i and j [%].

Variables

- $pg_{i,k}^{fs}$ Final active power of the FSP k of bus i [kW].
 $pl_{i,k}^{fs}$ Final active power load of the FSP k of bus i [kW].
 $pg_{i,k}^{fsh}$ Virtual active power output of the fixed shunt in bus i [kW].
 $p_{i,j,k}$ Active power in line between buses i and j [kW].
 $qg_{i,k}^{fs}$ Final reactive power of the FSP k of bus i [kVAr].
 $ql_{i,k}^{fs}$ Final reactive power load of an FSP k of bus i [kVAr].
 $qg_{i,k}^{ssh}$ Reactive power output of the switched shunt in bus i [kVAr].
 $qg_{i,k}^{fsh}$ Virtual reactive power output of the fixed shunt in bus i [kVAr].
 $q_{i,j,k}$ Reactive power in line between buses i and j [kVAr].
 v_i Magnitude of voltage of bus i [p.u.].
 Δv_i Voltage difference respect to the reference in bus i [p.u.].
 θ_i Angle of bus i, such that $\Delta\theta_{i,j} = (\theta_i - \theta_j)$ is a summary expression of the angle difference between bus i and bus j
 $\alpha_{i,k}$ Active power variation of the FSP k of bus i [kW].
 $q\alpha_{i,k}$ Reactive power variation of the FSP k of bus i [kVAr].
 $\beta_{i,k}$ Active power load variation of the FSP k of bus i [kW].
 $q\beta_{i,k}$ Reactive power load variation of the FSP k of bus i [kVAr].
 $y_{i,j}$ Binary variable. 1 when the last 10% line capacity is used between nodes i and j. 0 otherwise.

address the proper coordination between TSO and DSO under a high distributed energy resources (DERs) penetration scenario to improve the power system efficiency, quality, and flexibility.

1.1. Literature review

A high interest has been aroused in the study of the proper coordination between TSO and DSO to manage the high DERs penetration and address network issues under a flexible market scheme. Thus, some articles have reviewed the multiple schemes and models presented in the last years to manage this coordination problem, proposing different categorizations. The work developed in [1] reviews the different available schemes in the literature, grouping them into three TSO-DSO coordination models. The first model corresponds to a fully centralized dispatch managed by the TSO, while the DSO only provides real-time operational data. The second scheme identified by [1], the TSO, continues being the centralized entity that dispatches the energy, but in this case, the DSO validates the DER services bids to guarantee network integrity. In the third group, the DSO acts as the central coordinator of DER, validating bids and providing them to the TSO as an aggregated volume of services. A similar categorization is developed in [2] where the main differentiation criteria corresponds to the DSO role in managing the DERs. Thus, in [2] the DSO is defined as a leader when the DSO clears the local market and identifies the remaining (resp. surplus) energy to import (resp. export) from the TSO. In contrast, when the DSO takes the prices or the energy quantity fixed in the transmission and distribution connection point by a centralized market operator is a follower DSO, since the energy provided by DERs is subject to the quantity or price fixed by the market operator. For a deeper review of the different coordination schemes proposed in the last years, we suggest to the reader the analysis developed in [3].

Other works started addressing the coordination issue described above using different optimization techniques and market paradigms. For example, the paper in [4] addresses the required coordination scheme that allows the DSO to contribute to the system stability through ancillary services using a market model based on the power transfer distribution factor. Likewise, a bilevel optimization is used in [5] to coordinate the day-ahead operational planning between TSO and DSO using an extension unit commitment problem. The optimal power flow problem (OPF) is used in [6] to estimate the flexibility range of active and reactive power at the TSO-DSO boundary nodes and is also used by [7] to simulate a flexibility services market through the coordination between

TSO, DSO, and the retailer. In the same line of research, the work presented by [8] the ancillary services supplied by the DSO to the TSO in terms of congestion management and energy balancing are addressed using the DC power flow constraints.

In contrast to the previous approaches, other authors have addressed the TSO/DSO coordination problem using decomposition algorithms. For example, the authors in [9] use a convex relaxation of the AC OPF to build a hierarchical coordination mechanism for coordinating the large-scale energy supplied by DERs between DSO and TSO through a generalized bid function that separates the TSO and DSO requirements using the Bender decomposition method. A two-stage robust optimization approach is presented in [10] to manage the uncertainty of the FSPs, decomposing the TSO-DSO coordination problem in a transmission problem and multiple DSO subproblems using the well-known accelerated augmented Lagrangian method. In the same line of research, the authors in [11] propose a heterogeneous decomposition algorithm to separate the TSO and DSO. Continuing with the decomposition methods, the authors in [12] use a quadratic approximation function to improve the rate convergence of the decomposition algorithm based on the distribution-cost-correlation framework. Likewise, the work presented in [13] also uses a quadratic approximation to decompose the collaborative TSO/DSO problem into an upper TSO problem and multiples DSO lower problems to keep the information of every entity private and dispense of a coordinator. The same problem is solved in [14] using the analytical target cascading method, which belongs to the decomposition methods families available in the literature to address the autonomy of the subproblems regarding the master problem. In the same line, the hierarchical algorithms also have been applied in the TSO/DSO coordination problem in [15, 16] to solve the two-level optimization problem. The authors in [17] address the flexibility provided by the distributed generation resources of a DN to the TSO through a bi-level market clearing model, where the upper level corresponds to the transmission level and the lower level to the DN market clearing. Likewise, The work developed in [18] uses the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) to decompose the TSO/DSO coordination problem considering the three-phase unbalanced branch flow model, while the work in [19] proposes a dynamic two-stage AC OPF model to manage a DN with high DERs penetration,

such that the first stage address the day-ahead DN requirements and the second stage the intraday operation.

Under the previous research context, the European Union, aware of the potential benefits of efficient coordination between TSO and DSO, has promoted the study and implementation of empirical demo platforms to measure and test the TSO-DSO coordination schemes provided by the previous literature. For example, the SmartNet project compares five possible architectures for optimized interaction between TSO and DSO, including exchanging information for monitoring and acquiring ancillary services (reserve and balancing, voltage regulation, and congestion management), both for local needs and for the entire power system [20, 21]. Specifically, the schemes addressed in the project included: i) centralized AS market model, ii) local AS market model, iii) shared balancing responsibility model, common TSO-DSO AS market model, and iv) integrated flexibility market model, to test them under a projected 2030 scenario in Italy, Denmark, and Spain [22]. Likewise, the EvolvDSO project created two innovative algorithms based on the OPF constraints to coordinate TSO-DSO under existing/future market mechanisms [23, 24], which were tested in two real French DN (20-15 kV) and two Portugal DN (30-15/10 kV). Thus, in both projects, different coordination schemes have been analyzed using the OPF formulation as a base to simulate and test the cases in various frameworks, showing cost and power losses reduction in most cases.

1.2. CoordiNet Project

In November 2016, under the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package framework [25], the European Commission promoted the ancillary services, balancing and congestion management procurement by network operators from assets connected to the transmission and DNs in a coordinated way. In this regard, the CoordiNet project belongs to one of the Horizon 2020 program initiatives entitled TSO-DSO- Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage, and small-scale generation [26].

The project aims to demonstrate how DSO and TSO shall coordinate to procure and activate grid services most reliably and efficiently through the implementation of three large-scale

demonstrations [27] considering real networks from Greece, Spain, and Sweden. Specifically, demonstrate to which extent coordination between TSO/DSO will lead to a cheaper, more reliable, and more environmentally friendly electricity supply to the consumers through implementing three demonstrations at a large scale, in cooperation with market participants. Likewise, define and test a set of standardized products and the related key parameters for grid services, including the reservation and activation process for using the assets and, finally, the settlement process. Finally, specify and develop a TSO-DSO-FSPs/Aggregator cooperation platform starting with the necessary building blocks for the demonstration sites. These components will pave the way for the interoperable development of a pan-European market that will allow all market participants to provide energy services and opens up new revenue streams for consumers providing grid services.

In the above context, different study cases have been developed in Greece, Spain, and Sweden to assess market opportunities regarding efficient TSO-DSO coordination through congestion management, voltage management, and load/generation power balancing supplied by a flexible service provider (FSP). In this regard, for every large-scale demonstration, different tools have been developed or adapted to articulate the proper TSO-DSO coordination: a TSO tool, a DSO tool, an aggregation/flexibility provision tool, a sFSP management platform and a market-clearing tool. Nevertheless, considering that the electricity market structure and operation are different in every country involved in the project, the case studies addressed in this article correspond exclusively to the Spanish case where we focus on explaining the DSO tool operation.

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are two fold. Firstly, a DSO platform framework has been developed that integrates forecasting techniques, such as K-Nearest Neighbor and the Support Vector Machine algorithms, with a mixed-integer non-convex non-linear model based on OPF equations. This framework is used to manage the DN congestion and to keep the voltage within the operational range through active and reactive power control and a flexibility market. Secondly, two Spanish MV/LV DNs for future testing of TSO-DSO coordination are presented using the PandaPower package as a reference to validate power flows.

Figure 1: DSO platform scheme and Coordinet demo stakeholders.

The rest of the paper is summarized as follows. Section 2 describes the DSO platform structure, the methods used to generate the forecasts and the optimization model to manage the network congestions and the voltage management. Section 3 presents two real DNs where the mathematical model is tested. The different case studies are included in Section 4. Finally, the results are discussed in Section 5.

2. Distribution system operator platform

The Coordinet project developed different platforms to manage the DERs' flexibility services under a market-based scheme through coordinated communication between the TSO, DSO, and the Aggregators/FSPs, starting from a currently common platform, which already exists and is controlled by the TSO to manage congestion, balance, and voltage issues. Specifically, the project developed the TSO tool, the Aggregator/FSP tool, the local platform, and the DSO platform (see Fig. 1). Note that the local platform is a new development to manage local voltage/congestion problems and will be controlled by an independent operator, unlike the common platform, which the TSO currently commands to face global congestion/voltage issues. However, this article focuses mainly on the DSO platform developed and how it exchanges information with the other platforms.

2.1. DSO Platform structure

The DSO platform contains three functional modules that interact with the common and local platforms grouped under the Coordinet platform name, such that all the information exchanged

between the TSO, DSO, and Aggregators/FSPs is managed by this platform, as shown in Fig. 1. Within the DSO section, the Grid Observability module identifies which Business Uses-Case (BUC) will be activated in the following modules and uses internal historical data to forecast the load and the FSP generations to feed the intraday and day-ahead modules using the KNN and SVM algorithms depending on the type of module, as shown in Fig. 1. Likewise, both intraday and day-ahead modules independently execute the optimization model for their respective BUCs and operational time using their corresponding forecasted data.

Specifically, the day-ahead module estimates the DNs needs for the following BUCs: common congestion, local congestion, and local voltage control. i.e., depending on the BUC, some variables of the optimization model are activated or deactivated. Thus, the common congestion BUC considers the data forecasted from the observability module, executes power flow algorithms to replicate and detect congestion network problems, and runs the optimization model to mitigate these issues using the flexibility provided by the FSPs. The results are sent to the CoordiNet common platform, and the generation units correspond to those participating in the day-ahead spot market with units larger than 1 [MW]. On the contrary, the local congestion BUC considers units smaller than 1 [MW] and sends the results to the CoordiNet local platform; however, it operates similarly to the previous BUC. i.e., detects the DSO local needs running the optimization model to mitigate the issues identified by the power flow algorithms. Following the same logic, the voltage control BUC uses the optimization model to identify the flexibility provided by the FSPs to maintain the network voltage very close to a certain level defined by the DSO and send the results to the CoordiNet platform in a week-ahead timeframe.

The intraday module contrasts the expected grid operation provided by the observability module with the day-ahead market-clearing to compute through the optimization model the intraday market needs. This module is composed of the same submodules presented for the day-ahead module changing mainly the timeframe for all BUCs except the voltage control BUC, which sends reactive setpoints to the FSPs in a real-time timeframe.

2.2. Forecasting methods

Two approaches has been used to forecast the loads and the generators. In the case of the generators and loads that participate directly in the markets, the DSO has access to the market programs or baselines and thus it allows to have an accurate measurement of these units without the need of forecasting techniques. For the rest of the generators and loads units involved, machine learning techniques based on the historical data from DSO platform will be used in order to forecast their measurements. As shown in Fig. 1, this section will be part of the observability module.

Regarding the forecast techniques based on machine learning, two algorithms are used to forecast the active and reactive power generated and demanded considering the day-ahead and intraday time frameworks. The first algorithm, used in the day-ahead timeframe, is based on K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) [28], which is characterized by its simplicity and speed, without losing much performance compared to other more complex algorithms [29]. The second algorithm, related to the intraday timeframe, is based on the Support Vector Machine algorithm (SVM) [30]. Although it is a much more complex algorithm with higher execution times, it provides better precision regarding the real consumption and generation. Both algorithms have been chosen as references because their application has already been tested in electricity markets in [31, 32, 33, 34]. The day-ahead algorithm is executed every day and predicts the next 24 h (in around 60 seconds) based on historical data. The intraday algorithm is executed every hour (in about 5 minutes) and predicts only the next hour.

Going into detail about the forecasting techniques, on the one hand, the KNN presented in [29] is used. It has two hyperparameters that must be defined before running the algorithm. The first hyperparameter corresponds to the number of neighbors (K) from training data to be compared to test data. The embedding dimension (m) is the other hyperparameter that needs to be determined in advance, although it does not belong to KNN explicitly. It is used to create the features since there are not independent variables. It is made up of the seasonal length (s) and the window (w), i.e., $m = s \cdot w$. The hyperparameter s is always set to 24 to take entire days and w needs to be determined. Depending on this value, the features are formed by groups of w days. Further

Table 1
Machine learning approaches

	Day-ahead	Intraday
Algorithm	KNN	SVM
Hyperparameters	K, m	C, ε
Input	SCADA data of active and reactive power load and generation	
Output	Forecasted $PL_i^g, PG_i^{sg}, QL_i^g, QL_i^{sg}$	
Planning horizon	The entire next day	Next hour
Time resolution	Hourly	Hourly
Execution time	1 minute	5 minutes

detail can be found in [29]. On the other hand, the SVM algorithm uses the radial basis function kernel [35] and considers a regularization hyperparameter C that indicates to the SVM optimization how much is desirable to avoid misclassifying each training example. For large values of C , the optimization will choose a smaller-margin hyperplane if that hyperplane does a better job of getting all the training points classified correctly. Conversely, a minimal value of C will cause the optimizer to look for a larger-margin separating hyperplane, even if that hyperplane misclassifies more points. Likewise, the ε hyperparameter specifies the ε tube within which no penalty is associated in the training loss function with points predicted within a distance ε from the actual value. The choice of these hyperparameters in both models (KNN and SVM) is made heuristically through grid search cross-validation [36].

2.3. Optimization model

The mathematical formulation presented in this section considers the AC-OPF equations as a base to construct a general optimization model, which includes new variables and constraints to identify the active or reactive power that the FSPs should provide to address congestion and voltage problems for different uses-cases and modules minimizing the following expression.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Min } F = & \Lambda_1 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{k \in \Omega} (|\alpha_{i,k}| + |q\alpha_{i,k}| + |\beta_{i,k}| + |q\beta_{i,k}|) + \Lambda_2 \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} y_{i,j} + \\
 & \Lambda_3 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{k \in \Omega} (\Delta v_i) + \Lambda_4 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{k \in \Omega} (|pg_{i,k}^{fsh}| + |qg_{i,k}^{fsh}|). \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The objective function (1) is composed of four terms with which everyone has associated a respective penalize parameter, such that $\Lambda_1 \leq \Lambda_2 \leq \Lambda_3 \leq \Lambda_4$. The value of these parameters depends on every case, and the DSO defines them. However, their magnitude relationship is to ensure the order in which the variables are activated following the Coordinet project definitions. In this regard, the variables associated with Λ_1 are activated first, then the variables related to Λ_2 , Λ_3 , and Λ_4 depending on the BUC. Thus, if the market module runs the congestion BUC, the variables associated with the parameters Λ_1, Λ_2 , and Λ_4 will be considered. On the contrary, if the voltage control model is required, the variables related to the parameters Λ_1, Λ_3 , and Λ_4 will be activated. Specifically, the first term corresponds to the active and reactive power flexibility provided by the FSPs, such that the $\alpha_{i,k}$ variables represent the power injected into the grid, and the $\beta_{i,k}$ variables the power taken from the grid. Note that when the variable includes a q represents the reactive power; otherwise indicates active power. Thus, when it is required, these variables are activated and penalized through the parameter Λ_1 . The second term is associated with the binary variable that provides an extra line capacity between a security level defined by the DSO and the maximum technical line capacity. Thus, if the security level is, e.g., 90%, we ensure the lines use lower than 90%; otherwise, it is penalized in the objective function through the parameter Λ_2 . The third term penalizes the voltage deviation regarding a reference voltage defined by the DSO through the parameter Λ_3 , and the fourth term penalizes the provision of the virtual active and reactive power from the fixed shunts by means Λ_4 , which are considered to avoid infeasibilities. Note that the virtual concept indicates that these variables provide the required flexibility only in the extreme case of the optimization model infeasibility. i.e., if the flexibility available by the FSPs is not enough to mitigate congestion/voltage problems, these virtual variables will be activated. Therefore, the general model is subject to the following constraints.

The Eqs (2) and (3) corresponds to the active and reactive nodal power equations, respectively. Specifically, the righthand side of Eq. (4) considers, from left to right, the power provided by the static generators, the fixed electricity demand of the grid, the active power supplied by the fixed shunts, and the power provided or absorbed by the FSPs connected to the bus. Similar to Eq. (4)

, Eq. (5) include the reactive power from the static generators, the reactive power demand of the network, the reactive provided by the fixed shunts, the reactive power flexibility delivered by the FSPs, and the reactive supplied by the switches shunts.

$$v_i^2 G_i + v_i \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} v_j (G_{i,j} \cos(\Delta\theta_{i,j}) + B_{i,j} \sin(\Delta\theta_{i,j})) = p_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (2)$$

$$-v_i^2 B_i + v_i \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} v_j (G_{i,j} \sin(\Delta\theta_{i,j}) - B_{i,j} \cos(\Delta\theta_{i,j})) = q_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (3)$$

$$p_i = PG_i^{sg} - PL_i^g + \sum_{k \in \Omega} pg_{i,k}^{fsh} + pg_{i,k}^{fs} - pl_{i,k}^{fs}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (4)$$

$$q_i = QG_i^{sg} - QL_i^g + \sum_{k \in \Omega} qg_{i,k}^{fsh} + qg_{i,k}^{fs} - ql_{i,k}^{fs} + qg_i^{ssh}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (5)$$

$$v_i v_j (G_{i,j} \cos(\Delta\theta_{i,j}) + B_{i,j} \sin(\Delta\theta_{i,j})) - G_{i,j} v_i^2 = p_{i,j}, \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L} \quad (6)$$

$$v_i v_j (G_{i,j} \sin(\Delta\theta_{i,j}) - B_{i,j} \cos(\Delta\theta_{i,j})) + v_i^2 (B_{i,j} - Bs_{i,j}) = q_{i,j}, \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L} \quad (7)$$

$$\sqrt{(p_{i,j})^2 + (q_{i,j})^2} \leq S_{i,j}^{max} (SL_{i,j} + (1 - SL_{i,j})y_{i,j}), \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L} \quad (8)$$

$$pg_{i,k}^{fs} = PG_{i,k}^a + \alpha_{i,k}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (9)$$

$$qg_{i,k}^{fs} = QG_{i,k}^a + q\alpha_{i,k}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (10)$$

$$pl_{i,k}^{fs} = PL_{i,k}^a + \beta_{i,k}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (11)$$

$$ql_{i,k}^{fs} = QL_{i,k}^a + q\beta_{i,k}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (12)$$

$$0 \leq pg_{i,k}^{fs} \leq \overline{PG}_{i,k}^{fs}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{QG}_{i,k}^{fs} \leq qg_{i,k}^{fs} \leq \overline{QG}_{i,k}^{fs}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (14)$$

$$\underline{PL}_{i,k}^{fs} \leq \beta_{i,k} \leq \overline{PL}_{i,k}^{fs}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (15)$$

$$\underline{QL}_{i,k}^{fs} \leq q\beta_{i,k} \leq \overline{QL}_{i,k}^{fs}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \Omega \quad (16)$$

$$\underline{QG}_i^{ssh} \leq qg_i^{ssh} \leq \overline{QG}_i^{ssh}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (17)$$

$$V_i^{min} \leq v_i \leq V_i^{max}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (18)$$

$$|V^0 - v_i| = \Delta v_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (19)$$

The Eqs. (6) and (7) represent the lines flow constraints corresponding to the classical AC-OPF formulation.

Eq. (8) bounds the active and reactive power flow within the lines to the maximum apparent line power through a binary variable, providing an extra line capacity when needed. Specifically, the parameter $SL_{i,j}$ is a safety percentage of the apparent power defined by the operator (e.g., 90%), which guarantees decongested lines. However, for high loads levels, the binary variable can provide the remaining apparent power line capacity affecting the network congestion but avoiding infeasibility in the optimization problem. Thus, the binary variable activation is penalized in (1), to use it only in the critical cases and forcing the formulation to use other lines or the use of the FSP flexibility to decongest the grid before operating the lines close to its apparent power limits.

Eqs. (9) and (10) represent the active and reactive power flexibility provided by the FSP to the network when the FSP operates as a generator. Thus, the parameters PG^a y QG^a corresponds to the active and reactive power awarded in the spot market, and the variables (penalized in (1) to be used only when the power awarded generates lines congestion) indicate the power amount that must be reduced or increased to reduce the lines congestion. i.e., when $\alpha_{i,k}$ takes positive values, the power awarded must increase and decrease when $\alpha_{i,k}$ takes negative values.

Eqs. (11) and (12) represent the FSP flexibility when works as a load, such that PL^a and QL^a indicate the load consumption awarded and β the required variations to reduces the lines congestion.

Likewise, the Eqs. (13)-(16) bounds the flexibility supplied by the FSPs. Eq. (17) limits the reactive power provided by the switches shunts, (18) the voltage levels, and (19) the voltage variation regarding the reference voltage.

3. Distribution system description

In this study, two networks from the project are taken into consideration. These two networks represent real Spanish DNs, which include a MV and a MV/LV network. As network data is highly confidential, certain aspects of the networks have been omitted, such as the exact names of the resources, the substations, and the characteristics of the cables/overhead lines and transformers.

Table 2

Characteristics of the MV Grid FSP units

FSP	Resource	Units	Total capacity [MW]	Voltage [kV]	FSP connection level	Sub connection with TSO
WF1	Wind	17	10.68	66	Distribution	SS1
WF2	Wind	16	32	66	Distribution	SS1
WF3	Wind	21	42	20	Distribution	SS2
WF4	Wind	12	6	20	Distribution	SS2
PV	Solar	123	12.3	20	Distribution	SS2

This is done in a way that allows to protect sensitive data, but at the same time provide sufficient parameters for the replication of the results.

3.1. MV network description

Figure 2.a shows the simplified representation of the MV network used in the study and where the resources are connected. The network consists of two HV/MV substations 400/66 [kV], forty MV/LV substations, 66/20 [kV] and 66/15 [kV], seventeen MV lines and five FSPs.

The resources are connected to two different HV (400 [kV]) substations, SS1 and SS2, through transformers that change the voltage level from 400 [kV] to 66 [kV]. At SS1 substation, two wind farms are connected, WF1 and WF2. At SS2, a MV network is connected that includes two wind farms (WF3 and WF4) and one photovoltaic solar plant PV1. These substations are generally operated with only one connection between them, but there is a line connecting the substation of WF3 to the substation SS1. Under normal operational conditions, this line is usually opened, and during the development of the demos, it will remain open. In this way, all resources can be available to provide flexibility services required at both substations but with different sensitivities or impacts on relieving constraints.

The characteristics of the five FSPs connected to the MV network are shown in Table 2.

3.2. MV/LV network description

Figure 2.b shows the simplified representation of the MV/LV network used in the study and the connections of the resources in it. The grid consists of one MV/MV substation 66/20 [kV], one MV line, thirteen MV/LV secondary substations 20/0.4 [kV], ten MV consumers and one FSP. In

Figure 2: Simplified representation of the two Spanish networks

the MV/LV network, the FSP is a biogas plant connected at 20 [kV]. The characteristics of the FSP connected to the MV/LV network include four biogas units with a total capacity of 3.2 [MW], of which 2.0 [MW] are manageable.

4. Computational results

This section measures the model performance considering the PandaPower [37] for the MV and MV/LV networks. Besides, two exercises are developed to observe the active and reactive power variation when the voltage and the line capacity limits are modified. Then, a case study is analyzed using the real visualization provided by the DSO platform. To end, a discussion of the model limitation and future research is provided. The optimization model has been programmed in Python 3 [38] using Pyomo package [39] and Bonmin as the solver.

4.1. Time series prediction accuracy

The historical data related to the electricity demand and the active and reactive power generation was provided by the DSO to train the day-ahead and intraday forecasting algorithms. However, the data available consisted only of the consumption or generation reading point, without considering other correlated variables that could affect the data, like days of the week, holidays, and behavior patterns. In this regard, both algorithms presented in this article and used in the Coordinet project

are univariate, which could be extended to multivariate algorithms in future works to improve the algorithms prediction.

4.2. Model validation

The two Spanish DN presented in the above section have been tested using the PandaPower [37] software and the power flow equations belonging to the optimization model described in 2.3. The comparison aims to validate the model proposed using well-known software and provide a reference comparison point of the two Spanish networks for future research. In this regard, Fig. 3 and Table 3 show the comparison results between PandaPower and the model proposed, considering active and reactive power injected, losses, voltage levels, and the power provided by the FSPs and the external grid. The detailed data of every network and the parameters used to test the model are available in the supplementary material.

Fig. 3 shows the voltage comparison for both networks. Thus, the voltage levels provided by the model have an average difference of 0.02% regarding the voltage obtained through PandaPower simulation for the MV network, where the highest differences correspond to buses 19 with a WP and 48 (static generator), with an error of 1.49% and 1.35%, respectively. On the contrary, the voltage levels in the MV/LV network follow the same pattern with only an average error of 0.18%. The difference between the errors in the MV network with the MV/LV network is explained by the resolution method to solve the power flow problem. Specifically, PandaPower uses the Newton-Raphson method to solve the power flow (PF) problem, while Bonmin solves the PF through the branch-and-bound algorithm. Thus, despite both tools (Model proposed and PandaPower) providing close solutions (see Table 3), the active and reactive power amounts injected by the different network resources change slightly.

Table 3 shows the differences between both resolution methods for the two networks presented in this article. Thus, the voltage deviation explained above is justified since both networks' total active and reactive power injected into the system are almost equal; however, the generation sources

Figure 3: Voltage comparison.

Table 3

Power flow results comparison between PandaPower and the model proposed

Variable	MV network		MV/LV network	
	Model	PandaPower	Model	PandaPower
PG [MW]	1935.63	1934.84	3.2	3.22
PL [MW]	1897.87	1897.87	3.15	3.15
QG [MVA _r]	1465.56	1463.50	1.66	1.55
QL [MVA _r]	1210.09	1210.09	1.53	1.53
P Losses [MW]	37.76	36.97	0.051	0.072
Q Losses [MVA _r]	255.47	253.41	0.13	0.02
V min [p.u.]	0.987	0.985	1.03	1.03
V max [p.u.]	1.035	1.041	0.932	0.929
FSP [MW]	7.93	12.626	0.58	0
SGEN [MW]	228.17	243.54	0	0
Grid [MW]	1699.53	1678.67	2.62	3.221

change. The model supplies the electricity demand by injecting more active power from the external grid, while PandaPower uses more FSPs and static generators.

4.3. DSO platform functionalities

Part of the DSO platform functionalities corresponds to identifying the active and reactive power variability when the voltage or line capacities limit changes. In this regard, two exercises have been included in this section, considering the MV network. Thus, the *voltage exercise* modifies the reference voltage from 0.98 [p.u.] to 1.05 [p.u.] measuring the voltage behavior, its effect on the loadings, and the active and reactive power injected by the grid and the FSPs. On the other hand, the *loading exercise* measures the same effect as the previous case but restricts the line capacities.

(a) Voltage exercise: Voltage level

(b) Voltage exercise: Loading level

(c) Loading exercise: Voltage level

(d) Loading exercise: Loading level

Figure 4: Voltage and loading exercises in the MV network

Fig 4 shows the voltage and line capacities variation for voltage exercise in the upper row and the loading case in the lower row. The exercises include the voltage and loading levels obtained in the previous section (using only the PF - see Fig. 3) as a reference point to observe the improvements when the full model 2.3 is implemented. Thus, the voltage exercise in Fig. 5.a shows a voltage stabilization around V^0 and a reduction in the peak loading levels (Fig. 5.b) using the active and reactive power shown in Table 4. In other words, by sharing the active power supplied by the external grid between the FSPs and the local generators and increasing the reactive power, the congestion management model reduces the loading levels and stabilizes the voltage across the network. Likewise, in the loading exercise, when the capacities of the lines begin to be restricted in a decreasing way, the voltage levels reach the minimum and maximum allowed. Besides, in the limit case with a line capacity bound to 60% or 50%, the line between buses 6 and 46 exceeds its constraints of 60% or 50% and uses 100% of its line capacity to keep the remaining buses stable.

Tables 4 and 5 show the active and reactive power injection to manage the voltage levels and the line capacity constraints in Fig. 4. Specifically, in the voltage exercise, Table 4 shows a stable active

Table 4

Active and reactive power variation in the voltage exercise

Bus	Active Power					Reactive Power				
	v=0.98	v=1.0	v=1.02	v=1.05	v ref	v=0.98	v=1.0	v=1.02	v=1.05	v ref
4	12.88	12.88	12.88	12.88	1.58	0	0	0	0	0.49
5	400	400	400	400	0	32.49	-117.52	-200	-200	42.08
6	30	30	6.22	0	0	-15	-15	-15	-15	-1.66
8	10	10	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	-10.71
9	33.23	52.89	55.64	69.58	0	-23.65	-26.14	-27.22	-29.42	-17.16
10	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	2.84	0	0	0	0	-0.18
16	400	400	400	400	0	-70.87	-6.02	47.63	99.69	-55.56
17	149.01	137.47	146.41	89.26	1699.53	-4.25	26.95	0.14	-136.25	-27.95
18	88.9	81.33	93.75	148.67	0	-23.91	-24.64	-25.74	-26.55	25.85
19	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	0	0	0	0	0	4.62
29	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.51	0	0	0	0	-0.07
31	40	40	40	35.43	0	20	20	20	20	-2.78
47	366.01	366.15	366.33	366.52	0	46.4	43.72	41.61	38.32	30.73
48	366.01	366.15	366.33	366.52	228.17	46.4	43.72	41.61	38.32	35.26

power injection. Still, unlike the PF reference case, the model shares the generation through the FSPs and the static generators. However, the reactive power required to fulfill the voltage reference increase significantly when the voltage moves from 1 [p.u.] to 1.05 [p.u.]. A similar pattern is followed by the loading exercise in Table 5, where the reactive power increase when the capacities of the lines start decreasing.

4.4. DSO platform visualization

This section shows a real representation of the DSO platform developed for the Spanish demonstration in the CoordiNet project using the model described in previous sections. Thus, Fig. 5 collects three examples of the platform operation when some congestion arises. In this regard, the first capture (Fig. 5.a) corresponds to a partial representation of the MV network and shows congestion detected through the optimization model after receiving the information provided by the TSO and the energy awarded in the markets. Then, the second capture (Fig. 5.b) shows the technical limitation detected by the model, which is reported to the TSO to reduce the power provided by the FSP and avoid line congestion. The third capture (Fig. 5.c) indicates, for a period of 24 h, how the model manages the reactive power supplied by an FSP to avoid voltage issues in the network.

Table 5

Active and reactive power variation in the loading exercise

Bus	Active Power					Reactive Power				
	SL=50%	SL=60%	SL=70%	SL=80%	SL ref	SL=50%	SL=60%	SL=70%	SL=80%	SL ref
1	0.69	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	12.88	10.62	12.88	12.88	1.58	0	0	0	0	0.49
5	400	400	389.03	400	0	-200	-154.5	-200	-145.7	42.08
6	30	30	30	30	0	-15	-15	15	-15	-1.66
8	10	15.99	31.56	10	0	0	0	0	0	-10.71
9	9.99	13.83	20.34	16.98	0	-10.35	-13.45	-5.24	-23.54	-17.16
10	4.8	12.3	12.3	4.8	2.84	0	0	0	0	-0.18
16	400	400	400	400	0	-6.09	200	114.99	4.08	-55.56
17	87.81	100.57	114.18	128.47	1699.53	-35.74	11.92	20.86	36.17	-27.95
18	116.75	249.47	298.73	207.11	0	-11.49	-67.62	118.53	-25.49	25.85
19	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	0	0	0	0	0	4.62
29	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.51	0	0	0	0	-0.07
31	19.16	20.3	23.44	40	0	20	4.14	-1.3	20	-2.78
32	0.99	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
47	404.63	245.09	285.31	325.96	0	33.88	21.16	31.14	34.07	30.73
48	404.63	405.7	285.31	325.96	228.17	33.88	59.19	31.14	34.07	35.26

The yellow line represents the FSP active power, the orange and red lines the reactive power limits of the FSP, the green line the reactive power setpoint computed by the DSO platform, and the blue line the real FSP reactive power measured by the TSO. Note that the green and blue lines are not similar since the FSP commonly does not provide reactive power in real operation. However, in the capture it can be seen, that in Fig. 5.c between 9:20 and 10:20, when the demo took place, the reactive power setpoint are sent by the DSO platform to the TSO, the TSO forwards to the FSP and the FSP provides the necessary reactive power (blue line) to stabilize the voltage following the reactive power sent by the DSO platform (green line).

4.5. Discussion and future research

The deterministic model presented in section 2.3 has been programmed to be executed at every time interval, which means it is a single-period model. Therefore, future improvements for the model could be focused on extending it to a multiperiod model of 24 h, or reformulating it as a stochastic multiperiod model to manage the market FSP stochasticity. In this regard, the model was designed and programmed as a single-period formulation, considering the classic AC-OPF

(c) FSP performance

Figure 5: DSO platform screenshot

constraints to follow the Coordinet project requirements. However, a second-order cone relaxation could be applied to the proposed formulation to extend the model to multiperiod and reduce the computation burden due to the formulation as it has been presented; under a multiperiod context, it would significantly increase the computational time.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented a DSO platform framework for the Spanish demonstration of the Coordinet project. Thus, a mixed-integer optimization model has been introduced to use the flexibility services

that could provide the DERs in the day-ahead and intraday markets to face network congestion or voltage issues at the distribution level. Besides, two real Spanish DNs have been adapted to test the proposed model and be used in future research. In this regard, the software PandaPower has been used to validate the MV and MV/LV networks operation solving the power flow problem and contrasting the PandaPower results with the model proposed.

Two exercises have been developed to show the model's capacity to manage congestion and voltage issues through the flexibility supplied by the DERs. In both cases, the deterministic model reduces network congestion and stabilizes the voltage levels using the active and reactive power offered by the FSPs in the day-ahead and intraday markets. This shows that the flexibility services provided by DERs, through coordination between TSO and DSO, emerge as a potential alternative to face congestion issues. As a result, a reduction of the investments in network reinforcements can be expected.

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